

Chlorhexidine in Endodontics-II

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Substantivity

The effectiveness of Chlorhexidine stems from its capacity to adsorb to negatively charged surfaces in the mouth (e.g. tooth, mucosa, pellicle, restorative materials), being slowly released from these retention sites and therefore maintaining prolonged antimicrobial activity for several hours. This process is known as substantivity, and only chlorhexidine and tetracycline have this property so far.

Regarding its substantivity, it has been found that the use of chlorhexidine as root canal irrigating substance prevented microbial activity from 48 hrs, 7 days (in the liquid and gel formulation).

It seems that the antimicrobial substantivity is related to the chlorhexidine molecules available to interact with the dentin. Furthermore, the outstanding substantivity of chlorhexidine to dentin (evaluated at an interval from 0.5 h to 8 weeks) and its reported effect on the inhibition of dentinal proteases may explain why chlorhexidine can prolong the durability of resin-dentin bonds, particularly in the presence of collagen.

Chlorhexidine & Biofilms

A biofilm can be defined as communities of microorganisms attached to a surface, embedded in an extracellular matrix of polysaccharides. Within these microcolonies, bacteria have developed into organized communities with functional heterogeneity. It constitutes a protected mode of growth that allows survival in a hostile environment. Bacteria in such an environment differ greatly in phenotype when compared with their planktonic counterparts, and are far less susceptible to antimicrobial killing. It has been reported that

microorganisms grown in biofilms could be 2-fold to 1000- fold more resistant than the corresponding planktonic form of the same organisms.

Several studies using a single-species biofilm model and apical dentin biofilm have reported that higher concentration of NaOCl (varying from 2.25% to 6%) and chlorhexidine solution (2%) were effective against the tested microorganisms. The mechanical agitation improved the antimicrobial properties of the chemical substances, favouring the agents in liquid presentation, especially 5.25% NaOCl and 2% Chlorhexidine. Although chlorhexidine is effective against bacterial biofilms, NaOCl is the only irrigation solution with the capacity of disrupting biofilms.

Chlorhexidine & Coronal Microleakage

Canals medicated with chlorhexidine alone or in combination with calcium hydroxide retard the entrance of microorganisms through the coronal portion of the tooth into the root canal system, due to its wide antimicrobial activity and substantivity. Such a finding is interesting, especially if the coronal restoration becomes defective or if it is lost.

Regarding coronal microleakage during the intracoronary bleaching, it was found that chlorhexidine used as a vehicle for sodium perborate enhanced its antimicrobial activity and did not affect adversely dentin microhardness.

Tissue Dissolution Capacity

As far as the use of an auxiliary chemical substance in Endodontics is concerned, several studies have been performed in the search for a substance with major desirable properties for root canal irrigation, which includes the capacity to dissolve organic tissues. The tissue dissolution capacity of a substance depends mainly on three

factors:

- the frequency of shaking,
- the amount of organic matter in relation to the amount of irrigant in the canal system
- and the surface area of tissue that is available for contact with the irrigant.

Chlorhexidine gluconate has been recommended as a root canal irrigant because of its broad spectrum antimicrobial action, substantivity and low toxicity. However, chlorhexidine's incapacity of tissue dissolution has been pointed out as its major disadvantage. Some attempts have been made to evaluate the activity of chlorhexidine to dissolve organic matter, demonstrating that both preparations of this substance, aqueous solution or gel, were not able to dissolve pulp tissues. Bleeding in case of vital pulp will stop only with the complete removal of the pulp tissue by a full instrumentation of the root canal within its whole extension. Therefore, when chlorhexidine is used as an irrigant, emphasis should be given to full canal instrumentation in order to remove all pulp tissue, as chlorhexidine does not promote a superficial necrosis.

Due to its viscosity and rheological action, which keeps the debris in suspension, the gel seems to compensate for chlorhexidine's inability to dissolve pulp tissue, by promoting a better mechanical cleansing of the root canal and removing dentin debris and remaining tissues. The mechanical properties of the gel seem to be the main factor for this difference because the same chemical agent in the liquid form showed lower cleaning efficiency, although presenting similar antimicrobial activity.

Another important fact to be pointed out is that due to the complexity of the root canal system, even irrigation with 5.25% NaOCl does not remove all debris and organic tissues. On the other hand, dentin and organic tissues that get in contact with chlorhexidine during irrigation maintain a prolonged antimicrobial activity, as chlorhexidine is slowly released from these retention sites. Furthermore, if chlorhexidine is extruded through the apex, it does not induce pain to the patients.

Interaction with Endodontic Irrigants

Due to its wide spectrum antimicrobial activity and its inability of dissolving organic tissues, an irrigation regimen has been proposed, in which NaOCl would be used throughout instrumentation, followed by EDTA, and chlorhexidine would be used as a final irrigant.

The combination of NaOCl and chlorhexidine has been advocated to enhance their antimicrobial properties, and the advantage of using a final rinse with chlorhexidine would be the prolonged antimicrobial activity due to the chlorhexidine substantivity. It has been reported that the antimicrobial effect of 2.5% NaOCl and 0.2% chlorhexidine used in combination was better than that of either component.

Apart from the antimicrobial aspect, the association of NaOCl with chlorhexidine leads to the formation of an orange-brown precipitate, resulting in a chemical smear layer that covers the dentinal tubules and may interfere with the seal of the root filling. In addition, this precipitate changes the colour of the tooth and is cytotoxic.

On investigation NaOCl and chlorhexidine, with and without EDTA, when used in combination as endodontic irrigants against *Enterococcus faecalis*, and verified that combining EDTA with NaOCl or chlorhexidine was more effective than using EDTA alone. However, chlorhexidine combined with EDTA also leads to the formation of precipitates, resulting in a chemical smear layer that covers the dentinal tubules. Regarding the orange-brown precipitate, it occurs due the presence of NaOCl, an oxidizing agent causing chlorination of the guanidino nitrogens of the chlorhexidine. Thus, after chemo-mechanical preparation with NaOCl, the use of chlorhexidine as a final irrigant or as an intracanal medicament would require the removal of NaOCl from the canal.

It has been found that with regard to the use of NaOCl with chlorhexidine, 10 ml of distilled water in association or not with 17% EDTA and 10% citric acid was not enough to inhibit the formation of the chemical smear layer. In the cases where one wants to associate these substances, the protocol using phosphoric acid did not induce formation of chemical smear layer.

In summary, it is important to remove all traces of the substances used inside the root canals in order to avoid interactions between them.

*To be continued.....
(It's a review of literature and not an original article)*